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THE ROLE OF AMIR TEMUR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MARTIAL ARTS

Annotation: *The development of martial arts in the main military campaigns of Amir Temur. The art of masterpiece. Amir Temur's commanding talent was evident during his campaigns against Tokhtamysh and in India, as well as in his struggles against the Turkish Sultan Boyazid Yildirim, and against Tokhtamyshkhan on June 18, 1391 on the Kunduzcha River (present-day Samara in Russia). province), the battle on the Terek River (between the present-day villages of Shedrinsky and Shyolkovsky) on April 15, 1395, and the historical greatness of Amir Temur, who performed a number of tasks assigned to him by history itself.*

Keywords: *Amir Temur, Tokhtamish, Golden Horde, Jochi Nation, White Horde, Amir, ruler, khanate, cunning, army, Russian prince, Movarounnahr, Khojand, Ural conquest of new lands, Kunduzcha River, Terek River, northern neighbor, Delhi Sultan Mahmud Shah, Boyazid's son Suleiman, Samarkand, Sahibkiran, hundreds of thousands of troops, entry into battle*

Amir Temur's march against Tokhtamyshkhan. Amir Temur knew the dangers of the Golden Horde. He kept a close eye on what was happening in the Jochi nation. From 1360 to 1380, that is, in 20 years, 25 khans exchanged in the Golden Horde. In 1375, Oriskhan, the ruler of the White Horde, decided to unite the two parts of the Jochi nation, the Golden Horde and the White Horde. The unification of the Hordes could pose a serious threat to the state of Amir Temur. Amir Temur skillfully took advantage of the situation to prevent this danger. Tokhtamish, the son of Toi Khoja, escaped from the White Horde in 1376 and came to Samarkand.

Amir Temur decided to use it to fight Oriskhan. Amir Temur thought that Tokhtamysh would be the leader of his policy in the Jochi nation. But the opposite happened. With the help of Amir Temur, Tokhtamysh, who became the khan of the White Horde, followed in the footsteps of Oriskhan, who began the struggle to unite the Jochi nation and create a powerful Golden Horde. Tokhtamysh, the ruler of the White Horde (1377), decided to take advantage of the defeat of his rival and fake khan Mamaykhan in the Kulikovo field against Russian Prince Dmitry Donskoy, and this year narrowed Mamaykhan's remaining army on the banks of the Kalka River. -mor made. After this

victory, Tokhtamysh became the khan of the supreme ruler of the Golden Horde and began to unite the two parts of the Jochi nation.

Disagreements between Amir Temur and the brave and cunning Tokhtamysh became an open struggle.

The ceasefire sought to restore the power of the Golden Horde during the Uzbek Khanate (1312-1320). He began military campaigns to conquer new lands. In 1386, Tokhtamysh's army invaded Azerbaijan. He captured Tabriz, looted and destroyed many cities in Azerbaijan. Amir Temur understood the threat posed to his country by his northern neighbor, the Golden Horde. Amir Temur could not make any marches as Movarounnahr was threatened from the north. In 1387-1388, Tokhtamysh, taking advantage of Amir Temur's absence from Movarounnahr, launched an attack on the interior of the state. After destroying small groups of troops encountered on the way, Tokhtamysh invaded the territory of Samarkand and Bukhara regions. The cities were surrounded by the Golden Horde. Amir Temur, who was in Iran at the time, sent 30,000 troops to Movarounnahr to help, and he returned to his homeland in a hurry. The ceasefire withdrew, but he persuaded the Khorezmian ruler Suleiman Sufi to unite against Amir Temur. These events forced Sahibkiran to make the fifth last march to Khorezm in 1388. He conquered Urgench and ended the rule of the Sufi dynasty.

The march of Tokhtamysh to Samarkand and Bukhara left no doubt in Amir Temur's mind that the struggle was not for the desire to occupy a separate territory, but for the struggle of Tokhtamysh against Sahibkiran's policies.

The last two of Amir Temur's three marches against Tokhtamysh (1389, 1391, 1395), especially his crushing on the Terek River in 1395, are of great interest in terms of the development of martial arts.

In the winter of 1391, Sahibkiran decided to eliminate the threat posed by Tokhtamysh and prevent the Golden Horde from forming an alliance with the Egyptian Mamluks against Timur's state. He ordered an army to be mobilized to begin the march against the ceasefire. Food stocks have been stockpiled for the army.

The assembled army left Samarkand and crossed the Syrdarya on a bridge near the city of Khojand. In Tashkent, Temur inspected his army. The fighters were ordered to have the necessary weapons and equipment. On January 19, 1391, during a military parade, Amir Temur declared war on the Jochi people. He lined up his army and assigned commanders to each convoy.

The challenge was to march through the desert with two hundred thousand troops. I had to walk 2,500 kilometers through the desert. Amir Temur carefully studied the situation and chose a path that would provide security from the enemy during the movement, and at the same time would not detect the army until it collided with the enemy. Amir Temur's army moved through Yassi (present-day Turkestan in Kazakhstan), Karchik, Sabron, and then to Sariuzen (Sarisu River), from where the Little Mountain and the Great Mountain (Golden Choku - Golden Pass Mountain in Kazakhstan) the present-day Karsakpay quarry on the banks of the Irrawaddy).

After a three-month march, the army was short of food. Therefore, Amir Temur strictly limited the distribution of food, and one fighter was given about 10 kg of flour for 2 months.

In May 1391, Amir Temur's army reached the banks of the Tobol River. By the time he reached the city of Tobol, the army was moving in secret. This indicates that Amir Temur managed to hide the movement of a large army from Tokhtam. After a long and arduous journey, the army was allowed to rest and hunt. Before reaching Tobol, Sahibkiran had no information about the enemy. The Tobol crossing, which had been demolished by the troops of the ceasefire, was restored and the army crossed the river. After regaining its strength, the army moved towards the Ural River. The stop was pre-ambushed in three convenient places across the Ural River. Amir Temur, as an experienced and skilful commander, did not lead the army in that direction without losing vigilance, on the contrary, the army swam across the river far above these crossings. He knew that Tokhtamysh had ambushed and was standing there with his army, and that the beys of the Golden Horde were waiting for help to arrive from Azov and other places where they usually spend the summer months.

The area between the Ural and Volga rivers was considered a convenient location for the Stop Army, as it was possible to set up ambushes and wage small wars against the oncoming side. Amir Temur decided to bypass the enemy's right wing, which could have cut off Tokhtamysh's retreat to the capital and the direction of the expected relief forces, as well as depriving him of access to ground conditions. At the same time, this maneuver was forcing the enemy to enter the battle.

Sahibkiran moved his army not from the lower reaches of the Samara River, but from the top to the confluence of the Samara Iyk River. The avant-garde (manglay) and then the center (slave) passed through the bridge. The right and left flanks of the army (dark and gloomy) swam across the river.

To prevent a sudden blow from the enemy, Amir Temur ordered the warriors not to leave their units, to prepare large and small shields, to dig trenches around the camp, to conduct constant reconnaissance, and not to light fires. He assigned 30,000 soldiers to patrol the camp, patrolling the area. In order to prevent further retreats of the Golden Horde fighters, Amir Temur's small detachments ambushed the units and units of the enemy.

On June 18, 1391, on the banks of the Kunduz River (now Samara region of Russia), a battle took place between the army of Amir Temur and Tokhtamish. About 400,000 warriors from both sides took part in this battle, which was one of the greatest battles of its time.

The fighting order of Amir Temur's army in this battle is fully reflected in the works of Nizamiddin Shami and Sharofiddin Ali Yazdi. It was created by Sahibkiran himself. Amir Temur was the first to organize a fighting order in the form of "seven hands", ie corps, which has never been used before. Ali Yazdi writes: "The ruler himself marched and lined up the army in seven armies. I have never heard of a king marching in this way. " He also said that

the enemy's army was several times larger than Amir Temur's army (a military unit of 500 men).

The fighting order of Amir Temur's army was as follows. Emir Suleiman the Magnificent commanded the line. This hand was followed by a second hand led by Mirza Muhammad Sultan. In Barangar, the hand of Mirza Mironshah was lined up, and the hand of Khoja Sayfiddin was lined up on the right wing, playing the role of a kunbul. Juvongor was composed of Mirza Umarshaikh's army. As for Kunbul, Berdibek Saribug's hand is on the left wing. The center of the army's fighting order was blocked by the avant-garde. Behind the front of the arm was a battalion under the command of Supreme Commander-in-Chief Amir Temur. 20,000 troops under the command of Amir Temur were reserved. These reserve forces played a decisive role in the outcome of the war.

On the opposite side, Khan Tokhtamish divided his army into five divisions, commanded by prominent commanders and the heroes of Dashti Kipchak. Before the war, Amir Temur used a mental attack. In order to influence the enemy's superstition and arouse hatred in the army, he ordered his grandson Mirza Abubakir's detachment to set up tents and cook in pots. All of this shocked the enemy so much that he froze.

Mirza Umarshakh attacked the enemy's barracks. Tokhtamysh did not dare to attack the center of Sahibkiran's army and decided to give the main blow to the left wing of Amir Temur's army. He personally led the attack. At the end of the battle, the Golden Horde's army broke through the left wing of Sahibkiran's army and threatened to surround it from behind. Taking into account the situation, Amir Temur and his troops entered the reserve into battle, and he decided the outcome of the battle in favor of Sahibkiran. Amir Temur's reserves crushed the bursting Golden Hordes. After the defeat of the army, Tokhtamishkhan was forced to concede defeat. At the height of the fighting, the flag of Tokhtamysh was dropped and his army began to flee.

In order to pursue the defeated Tokhtamysh's army, Amir Temur ordered seven warriors out of every ten. The pursuit was carried out along the banks of the Volga River, and was carried out so valiantly that the army of the Stop was dispersed, not knowing where its flag was, and not knowing where to gather, part of which was killed by gunfire. the second part sank into the river.

After defeating the enemy and capturing a large amount of booty, Amir Temur returned to Samarkand with his army (late October 1391).

The main results and training of this military march and battle are as follows:

1. Amir Temur's army carried out a planned march in difficult and difficult conditions, in which the road through the desert areas alone exceeded 2,500 kilometers.

2. Amir Temur's army passed through the difficult and difficult parts of the journey without the enemy noticing.

3. With his skillful maneuvers, Amir Temur cut Tokhtamish's army from the south, where additional support forces were likely to come from the Azov coast.

4. Sahibkiran, due to his skillful actions, forced Tokhtamysh to enter a big battle, thus depriving him of the opportunity to wage small wars aimed at exhausting the army of Amir Temur, who had made a difficult journey.

5. During the trip, Amir Temur's army crossed large and small barriers. Shallow crossings (bridges), bridges and sailing were used.

6. In the battle of Kunduz, Amir Temur was the first to introduce a new military order, dividing his army into seven parts. A powerful reserve has also been allocated.

7. Before the battle, Sahibkiran carried out a mental attack aimed at undermining the morale of the enemy.

8. The outcome of the battle was decided by the introduction of the reserve into battle and a powerful blow from the wing by Amir Temur.

9. The pursuit of the enemy was so intense that it dispersed or was crushed before it could gather together.

But the power of the Golden Horde was not completely destroyed. Tokhtamishkhan still had a lot of reserves to regain his strength. there was no doubt that a decisive battle was still ahead.

In 1391, Amir Temur's march to the Golden Horde and his victory over Tokhtamysh provided only temporary peace in the north of the state. The main economic bases of the stop were located on the lower Volga, in the Palace and Haji Tarkhan, and Amir Temur did not touch them during the march. Relying on these bases and bases in the North Caucasus, Crimea, Azov and elsewhere, Tokhtamysh quickly recovered from the coup and regained its former military power. At the end of the 14th century, he became an arch-enemy of Amir Temur. In the autumn of 1394, taking advantage of the presence of Amir Temur's army in northern Azerbaijan, Tokhtamish invaded Shirvan via Darband. stopped to rest nearby. He sent a vanguard of the Stop Army to guard the crossing of the Kuysu River. Defeating the enemy guards at the crossing, Amir Temur's army entered what is now Chechnya and Ingushetia. The confluence of the Sunji River with the Terek River was chosen to pitch tents. Amir Temur's army moved to the banks of the Sunji River to seize the crossings on the Terek River without delay.

By the time Amir Temur's army arrived, Tokhtamysh had managed to cross the Terek, build defensive structures, and fortify the left bank of the river with chariots, trees, and barriers. Nevertheless, Amir Temur managed to crush the enemy's vanguard and cross Sunji.

Now Amir Temur's army had to cross the Terek River. His army moved from the south (right) coast, and Tokhtamysh's army from the north (left) coast. By the time Amir Temur's army arrived, Tokhtamysh had managed to cross the Terek, build defensive structures, and fortify the left bank of the river with chariots, trees, and barriers. Nevertheless, Amir Temur managed to crush the enemy's vanguard and cross Sunji.

Now Amir Temur's army had to cross the Terek River. His army moved from the south (right) coast, and Tokhtamysh's army from the north (left) coast. To keep an eye on Amir Temur's army, Tokhtamysh set up guard units. Both sides continued to move along the river for three days. On the third day, Amir Temur ordered all women who came with the army to wear helmets and armor and to imitate the actions of the warriors. The warriors, on the other hand, were ordered to take two horses each and move quickly to reach the crossing.

Amir Temur's fighters marched for three more days and crossed Terek on the ninth day of the conflict.

On April 15, 1395, on the banks of the Terek River (between the present-day villages of Shedrinsky and Shyolkovsky), a battle took place between the armies of Amir Temur and Tokhtamysh. Before the battle, according to the rules of preparation for battle, Amir Temur ordered to strengthen and guard the camp, to be ready to repel the enemy's night attacks. Trenches were dug around the camp, poles were buried in the ground so impassable (mandu), and barriers were erected. The main ditches were blocked by red ditches in front. No movement inside the camp is prohibited.

This time, too, Amir Temur divided his army into seven divisions. In the center is the arm (center of the army), in front of the arm is the main avant-garde (hiraul), behind it is the chagdavul (aregard). On the wings of the army were the vanguards of the Barangar and the Jarongar. The main avant-garde was ahead of the wing avant-garde and served to break through the enemy's battle order. Chagdavul (aregard) acted as a reserve and was used to guard the rate.

Thus, the fighting order of Amir Temur's army consisted of three lines: the first - the avant-garde, the second - the main forces, and the third - the reserve.

The first line was made up of lightly armed warriors who started the battle, dispersing the enemy's fighting order and causing chaos in its ranks. The second line of troops was armed with heavy weapons and had to repel the enemy's attack. The center of the army formed the basis of the army and in many cases decided the fate of the battle. Light infantry units are located in front of the main avant-garde, center, left and right wings. The right and left wing vanguards, as well as the rearguard, consisted only of cavalry.

All of these units acted independently and were subordinate only to the Supreme Commander-in-Chief.

This line-up created the following advantages:

1. Continuous and massive attack on the enemy by cavalry and infantry;
2. The fact that the main part of the army was under the protection of the guards and the aregard (chagdavul), which in turn increased the stability of the defense and prevented the enemy from covering the wings and the rear of the front. According to his experience in the battle of 1391, Amir Temur convinced his army of the superiority of the military order and lined up his army in the same order as the Sahibkiran army.

The battle began with a powerful attack by the Golden Hordes on the army of Amir Temur's army. Given the difficult situation on the left wing, Amir Temur sent support forces from his reserves in that direction. The oncoming fighters repulsed the enemy's attack and began to pursue it themselves. Successful units were separated from the main forces.

The second day of the battle began again with the attack of Stop. He added his voice to the attack. The army of the ceasefire overthrew the vanguard of Amir Temur's army and attacked the barracks. Part of the army in Sahibkiran's barracks dispersed, and the other part dismounted and continued to rain arrows at the enemy. This part of the army was supported by other parts of Sahibkiran. On the second day of the battle, neither side won.

On the last or third day of the conflict, the battle began again with the attacks of the Golden Horde. Strengthening the center and wings, Tokhtamysh moved to the front. The sound of the stop was also heard in the battle. Amir Temur felt that this part of the army was weakening. Amir Temur delivered the main blow to the enemy. The cessation of hostilities was completely silenced. Amir Temur launched a decisive attack in all areas. Exhausted during the three days of fighting, the Golden Horde could not find the strength to resist, and as a result suffered a crushing defeat. He hid in his dreams.

This time Amir Temur was not satisfied with the outcome of the battle and decided to crush the sources of the main military power of the Golden Horde khanate. Continuing to pursue the enemy, Amir Temur led his army into the Dnieper River, where the Minkerman Fortress was destroyed. Returning from the Dnieper, Amir Temur headed for Russia and reached the city of Elets. Amir Temur then conquered the Caucasus, and then the main bases of the Golden Horde headed for Haji Tarkhan and the Palace.

In the spring of 1396, Sahibkiran's victorious army arrived in Azerbaijan.

The defeat of the Golden Horde by Amir Temur was instrumental in freeing the Mongol princes from the tyranny of the Russian princes.

In terms of the development of martial arts, the Battle of Tokhtamysh, especially the Battle of the Terek River in 1395, has the following characteristics:

1. Due to the military trick used by Amir Temur, he was able to lead his army across the Terek River without any danger or loss.

2. On the eve of the battle, Amir Temur equipped his camp and prepared it to repel a possible night attack by the enemy.

3. In this battle, both sides divided their armies into seven divisions.

4. Amir Temur's combat order was deeply established and ensured the stability of the defense and the effectiveness of the attack.

5. During the battle, Amir Temur's army used a variety of tactical methods - rapid attack, ambush, Quran (barrier created by chariots), cavalry on foot, etc.

6. Amir Temur managed to get out of a difficult situation by organizing effective interaction of the army, and then won the inevitable victory.

7. Choosing the right direction of the head on the right wing decided the outcome of the fight in the most difficult situation.

8. This battle was one of the greatest battles of the Middle Ages.

9. As a result, the power of the Golden Horde was dealt a severe blow, after which it was unable to regain its former power.

CONCLUSION

The historical greatness of Amir Temur is that he fulfilled a number of tasks assigned to him by history itself.

The first task is to unite the Central Asian region into a single centralized state.

The second task was the defeat of the Golden Horde by Amir Temur, after which the desert state could not regain its former power. This, in turn, hastened the weakening of his power over the Russian principalities and the complete liberation of united Moscow Russia from Mongol oppression.

The third task is related to the victory of Amir Temur over the Ottoman sultan Boyazid in 1402 near Ankara. By crushing the Ottoman army, Amir Temur divided it into smaller states. It took a long 50 years for this state to unite into another single state.

This half-century period was very important for the peoples of Eastern and Central Europe. He delayed the Ottoman expansion to the west by half a century. During this time, the fragmented states of Europe became much stronger.

In his speech at the opening ceremony of the Temurid Historical Museum on October 18, 1996, I.A. Karimov, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, said: united and raised the banner of freedom and built a strong centralized state. ”

REFERENCES:

1. Rustambek Shamsutdinov, Husanboy Mo'minov O'zbekiston tarixi "Fan" nashriyoti davlat korxonasi Toshkent-2020
2. Temur tuzuklari "Ochun" nashriyoti 2021
3. www.ziynet.uz axborot portal
4. <https://arboblar.uz>
5. <https://saviya.uz>
6. Irpon To'xtiev "Amir Temur va Temuriylarning moliya-pul siyosati" O'zbekiston NMIU 2006